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Editor-in-chief:

Maria A. Egorova. Professor at Competition Law Department, Kutafin Moscow State Law University (MSAL), Member of Executive Committee of Moscow Branch, Association of Russia's Lawyers; Chair of Commission for improvement of antitrust legislation at Moscow Branch of Association of Russia's Lawyers, Member Of the International Committee Digital Economy BRICS, Member of Committee for entrepreneurship security at Chamber of Trade and Industry of the Russian Federation, Prof h.c, LL.D, doctor of law, Associate Professor, Honorary Professor of Johann Heinrich Pestalozzi University Inc. (Florida, USA), Honorary Professor of Logos University (Miami, USA)

CONCEPT OF THE JOURNAL:

the journal is positioned as the first periodical printed edition dedicated to the aspects of financial regulation of digital economy in Russia and other states

READERS:

students and staff of legal departments of universities, state officials, lawyers specializing in legal regulation of digital economy, business and competition law, small and medium business, entrepreneurs, researchers, master and PhD students and all readers interested in the aspects and topical matters of developing legal regulation of digital economy in Russia and other states

MAIN THEMES:

- State regulation of the digital economy
- Legal regulation of crypto currency and mining
- Crowdfunding (problems and perspectives)
- Legal regulation of Big Data
- Technology of blockchains and cryptocurrency (bitcoin, Copernicus, Ethereum, etc.)
- Interests and contradictions associated with blockchains in Finance
- Financial technologies in the current Russian and international legal framework
- Digital technology in the sphere of intellectual property and innovation
- Legal status of smart contracts
- Protection of rights and legal interests of participants in digital markets
- Information security
- Consortiums in the industry web: legal nature and specifics of regulation

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ARE BLOCKCHAINS AND CYBERCURRENCIES DEMANDING A NEW LEGISLATIVE FRAMEWORK

Abstract. The digital economy and especially Blockchain technology are opening interesting new fields for regulating and legislative authorities. Some government representatives make the mistake to look at blockchain applications mainly as underlying technology for cryptocurrency technologies. But the technology can be used far wider as a way for secure decentralized data storage. Storing data on worldwide networks makes the blockchain applications difficult to regulate as they are not residing in a specific area of influence of any given regulation or jurisdiction. Also the blockchain applications offer an extensive level of anonymity to their stakeholders. In future artificial intelligence will start to optimize the applications and trigger decisions automatically which will become a major challenge for competition and anti-trust regulators as it will be difficult to define legal entities with responsibility for the action taken. Beside building up an appropriate regulation regime the inherent challenges in blockchain technologies will ask for a strong self-regulation of the market participants in the digital marketplace.

Keywords: Blockchain, Cryptocurrencies, antitrust law, competition law.

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Introduction

Rapid changes in the digital world have a sustainable influence on economics, legislation, commerce and even on human relations and society as a whole. Especially blockchain applications have become more and more prominent mostly by coverage in the media of today's leading blockchain application — Bitcoin. Blockchains are basically algorithm with decentralized data storage lacking a centralized administration. The software for most blockchain applications is open source and keeps the ledger of all transactions ever occurring on public files — small blocks of information on each computer building the network.

The inherent decentralizing aspects and anonymity of blockchain applications makes it difficult to define the appropriate jurisdiction. As published in the Harvard Business Review early 2017¹ the future increased value and importance of many blockchain applications will require

a close cooperation and deep collaboration of multiple stakeholders in the system. All participants on all levels of the process have to adopt and follow a common platform and procedure which will lead to industry consortia. The inherent decentralizing aspects of blockchains make it difficult to define an appropriate jurisdiction. In traditional law, and in absence of any agreement stating otherwise, blockchain disputes are normally settled by state courts. But the structure of blockchains are giving nearly insoluble problems to such state courts. Accepting that we are only seeing the first developments of these new markets allows us to start discussion about necessary steps to adapt regulations and compliance policies on an international level. Thus, given these scenarios, this paper aims to start discussing the possible frictions between blockchain applications and stakeholders and legislative and regulative authorities.

Blockchain Technology in short words

Blockchain has become more and more prominent in the last years. It is basically an algorithm with decentralized data storage, lacking a central administrator, and where the participants know

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* Breu S. U.,

Prof. h.c, DBA, Certified Fiduciary with Federal Diploma of Higher Education, President Johann Heinrich Pestalozzi University Inc., Florida, USA, Secretary General of the Swiss Centre for International Humanitarian Law

¹ *Iansiti M., Karim R. Lakhani.* The Truth About Blockchain // Harvard Business Review. January / February 2017. URL: <https://hbr.org/2017/01/the-truth-about-blockchain>.

nothing about each other. Best known as the technology behind bitcoin as the leading cryptocurrency, it is mostly understood as distributed ledger technology which is widely used today. Bitcoin and its underlying blockchain technology were first introduced by Satoshi Nakamoto in his paper «Bitcoin: A Peer-to-Peer Electronic Cash System»².

The whole software for cryptocurrencies is open source and keeps the ledger of all transactions ever occurring on public files. The records of all transactions are secured on the computers that build this ledger, but not the whole ledger on all but only small blocks with references to other blocks on all these computers worldwide, linked and secured using cryptography. This means, any alternation of any block cannot be done without alternation of all subsequent blocks which makes the system permanent, efficient and verifiable. So, each transaction and its identification is validated by at least three parties involved in maintaining the whole system and «mining» new blocks of information containing data relating to the actual transaction. By solving mathematical problems presented by the system these blocks are added to the existing blockchain, so all members of the system have access to the data. If a transaction is not verifiable with the existing blockchain the new blocks will not be integrated and so the integrity of the system is guaranteed.

Distributed ledger technology has been described as potential secure and efficient solution for several applications³. It is also widely expected that blockchains will track integrity and provenance of other special products like pharmaceuticals, diamonds or seafood in future. Blockchain will change the way of exchanging data and the ability to transact globally in various fields, including financial services. Beside the public blockchains, like the one used by bitcoin, there are new applications like consortium blockchains where the consensus process is limited to predefined nodes of the blockchain i.e. participants and members of the consortia. The access to the blockchain can be public or restricted or even hybrid. In a fully private blockchain the write permission is kept by one organization but it might

be possible to have public reading permission or even that could be restricted to certain stakeholders of the blockchain. In contrast to the public blockchains, consortium or private blockchains can easily change rules and entries in the ledger and even revert processes. But having a central entity controlling the blockchain and being capable of interfering with the algorithm, especially for the challenges discussed in this paper, might solve the problem to define a responsible legal entity and take legal actions against it. This makes a big difference to distributed ledger technology where such a legal entity is difficult to define.

Definition of Jurisdiction

Blockchain will change the way of securing and exchanging data and the ability to transact globally in various fields, including financial services. The inherent decentralizing aspects of blockchains make it difficult to define an appropriate jurisdiction. In traditional law, and in absence of any agreement stating otherwise, blockchain disputes are normally settled by state courts. But the structure of blockchains are giving nearly insoluble problems to such state courts.

Blockchain application will conduct business transactions completely independently from the physical location of the involved legal entities. So it is possible that the stakeholders of the blockchain are acting in various jurisdictions, the blockchain administrator (if any) operates in a third country and the data suppliers are domiciled yet in another jurisdiction. We have a similar problem as with cross-border transactions to define the applicable law. This raises new challenges to regulators like the decentralised storage on large computer networks, anonymity of participants and unspecified values exchanged where it is not sure if these «goods» are included in the United Nations Convention on Contracts for the International Sale of Goods.

As the courts and states have enormous problems to tackle in these new scenarios, self-regulation of the market participants will play an important role. One part of a consumer-friendly self-regulation could be dispute settlement by an arbitral tribunal. Such arbitral processes could also be individually tailored for stakeholders in a spe-

² Nakamoto Satoshi. A Peer-to-Peer Electronic Cash System. November 2008 // URL: <https://bitcoin.org/bitcoin.pdf>.

³ Plant R. Can Blockchain Fix What Ails Electronic Medical Records? // Wall Street Journal. 27.04.2017. URL: <https://blogs.wsj.com/experts/2017/04/27/can-blockchain-fix-what-ails-electronic-medical-records/>; Popper N., Lohr S. Blockchain, A Better Way to Track Pork Chops, Bonds, Bad Peanut Butter? // New York Times. 04.03.2017. URL: <https://www.nytimes.com/2017/03/04/business/dealbook/blockchain-ibm-bitcoin.html>; Rachel A. From Farm To Finished Garment: Blockchain Is Aiding This Fashion Collection With Transparency // Forbes. 10.05.2017. URL: <https://www.forbes.com/sites/rachelarthur/2017/05/10/garment-blockchain-fashion-transparency/#4975681774f3>.

cific blockchain application. Bitcoin with its underlying blockchain has already started to create a supranational economy in which the classical idea of a legal person is obsolete⁴ whereas the supranational law is not really designed to address these new developments yet.

Another opinion on this jurisdictional issue is: «that at a simple level, every transaction potentially comes under the legislative umbrella of wherever the node exists whether in respect of financial services or data protection»⁵. Whereas the author also states that this means that blockchains would then need to be compliant with a potentially unwieldy number of legal and regulatory regimes.

Given this, the locus of a relevant «act» could be unclear as the transactions may have occurred simultaneously in a few different places, which again makes it nearly impossible to determine the competent jurisdiction. The unsolved questions regarding competence of jurisdictions in these new challenges of the new digital economy will also soon concern antitrust and competition law considerably as blockchain technology and its surrounding architecture will develop into new spheres and have considerable impact on our daily life.

Legislative and Regulative Approaches

Whether in a distributed ledger, a blockchain consortia or a private blockchain a deep cooperation and interaction between stakeholders is necessary to take full advantage of the potential. Blockchain are unified platforms with unified processes to maintain its structures. Attention has to be paid to the fact that all information shared between the stakeholders are only used to help the consortia to achieve legitimate goals and not violate competition laws and regulations. In future artificial intelligence will open a completely new field as blockchains will start to operate independently to optimize prices and profits by using the data stored within the ledger and trigger decisions and actions automatically.

For state legislation it is very difficult to implement regulations that have to be followed in a system that is outside its sphere of influence and action. An autonomous system maintained and managed by the users themselves over which no stately organization has any influence and control might start a supranational economy in which the classical idea of a legal entity is obsolete.

Within this new digital economy there is no technical necessity for the stakeholders to be attached to any jurisdiction. The high degree of anonymity of stakeholders in a blockchain is also a challenge for legislation as for example will still do not know the real identity behind «Nakamoto Satoshi» who presented the first concept of bitcoin to the public back in 2008.

Switzerland (self-regulation)

Based on this view on difficulties to regulate blockchain applications and cryptocurrencies self-regulation of the market participants will play an important role. The Swiss Crypto Valley Association for example published the ICO Code of Conduct for Switzerland in January 2018. The Code of Conduct addresses the following points:

A. Business Conduct

Members do their business in a responsible and transparent way, and do not engage in practices which would be potentially or factually damaging to the image and interests of the CVA and the ecosystem. Members adhere at all times to the Codes and, beyond it, to the applicable laws and regulations.

B. Diversity and Inclusion

Members do not discriminate in the work environment based upon race, color, gender, sexual orientation, religion, age, national origin, or disability.

C. Books and Records

Members ensure adequate and truthful operating and financial accounting as well as a proper system to record their business files. Members notify to the CVA any changes of their address, email, mobile number, domain name.

D. Property Rights

Members respect property rights of others, such as intellectual property rights, brand names or copyrights associated with any crypto valley related business.

E. Governance and Conflicts of Interests

Members implement in their organizations governance policies to ensure proper operation and control and to avoid (potential) situations of conflict of interest.

F. True and Fair Communication

Members commit to full, accurate, timely and understandable communication. In compliance with their confidentiality obligations, members

⁴ *Starodubcev D.* Bitcoin created a supranational economy // CoinFox.info. 17.03.2016. URL: <http://www.coinfox.info/news/persons/5109-dima-starodubcev-bitcoin-created-supranational-economy>.

⁵ *Brandman G., Thampapillai S.* Blockchain — Considering the Regulatory Horizon // University of Oxford, Faculty of Law, Business Law Blog. URL: <https://www.law.ox.ac.uk/business-law-blog/blog/2016/07/blockchain-considering-regulatory-horizon>.

are encouraged to disclose any form of mismanagement, corruption, incident, illegality, wrongdoing and any other serious infringements of the rules in force at the CVA or of national or local laws, to the CVA Board of Directors.

G. Breaches / Disciplinary Action

Members accept that any breach of the Code can result in disciplinary actions, which, depending upon the nature and severity of the breach, include written warnings, information and/or remediation requests, and — in case of serious breaches — expulsion from the CVA. The Members shall always have the right to be heard and costs shall be allocated to the Member depending on the disciplinary action decided.

H. Transactions

Members shall remunerate transactions on an «arm's length» basis. Hence, any fees, salaries or «cost-plus» mark-ups shall be comparable with third-party transactions.

Gibraltar (governmental regulation):

This being an example of self-regulation through market participants Gibraltar through its Gibraltar Financial Service Commission published in October 2017 as one of the first governments a Distributed Ledger Technology Regulatory Framework:

1. A DLT Provider must conduct its business with honesty and integrity.

The GFSC must be satisfied that the applicant, including the persons associated with it, are fit and proper to undertake the DLT activity. The basic elements which are relevant to such an assessment include:

- honesty, integrity and reputation;
- skill, competence, care and experience; and
- financial position.

2. A DLT Provider must pay due regard to the interests and needs of each and all its customers and must communicate with its customers in a way which is fair, clear and not misleading.

DLT Providers are expected to devote as much time and consideration to protecting consumers' interests as to their own, and dedicate sufficient resources necessary to protect consumers. There is a need to use best endeavours to mitigate the risks associated with use of DLT and employ best practice in the operation of their business. DLT Providers must make appropriate disclosures regarding:

- the use of DLT in the business;
- the risks associated with the technology and its use by firm; and
- the products and services supplied and associated risks.

DLT Providers need to make initial and per-transaction disclosure of risks, terms and conditions, as well as employing ethical advertising and marketing standards. They must have adequate complaint policies and disclosures and be able to manage and disclose any conflicts of interest. DLT Providers need to ensure that the information is presented in a way that is likely to be understood by the target customer and does not disguise, diminish or obscure important items, statements or warnings.

3. A DLT Provider must maintain adequate financial and non-financial resources.

DLT Providers are expected to maintain sufficient financial resources to ensure that it can be run in a sound and safe manner. Capital levels must be monitored to ensure that sufficient capital is held to support business objectives. Capital level must be commensurate with the prudential risks. As a minimum, DLT Providers are expected to hold sufficient capital to ensure an orderly, solvent wind-down of its business. Where appropriate, DLT Providers are required to hold professional indemnity insurance cover. Consideration will therefore be given to the following:

- adequacy of financial resources;
- sustainability of business model;
- maintenance and retention of books and records; and
- audit and reporting standards.

In terms of non-financial resources, DLT Providers must ensure that it will be able to comply with the requirements imposed by the GFSC in the exercise of its functions.

4. A DLT Provider must manage and control its business effectively, and conduct its business with due skill, care and diligence; including having proper regard to risks to its business and customers.

DLT Providers are expected to apply good, forward-looking risk management practices. This will help provide assurance to all stakeholders that the core processes and systems are effectively controlled, are fit for purpose and that risk is being managed in the right way. Strong risk management practices will make DLT Providers better equipped to act on risks and control in a timely manner, therefore reducing the likelihood of significant risks emerging that have not already been identified and managed effectively.

5. A DLT Provider must have effective arrangements in place for the protection of client assets and money when it is responsible for them.

DLT Providers are expected to take all reasonable precautions to protect customer assets in

their custody or control against unexpected eventualities and threats. Custodial assets will need to be segregated from the DLT Provider's own assets. DLT firms need to ensure that they maintain robust and accurate records of transactions.

6. A DLT Provider must have effective corporate governance arrangements.

DLT Providers need to implement good corporate governance. This is crucial as it will establish the system by which firms will be run and business overseen, including its structure, processes, culture and strategies. It will establish the rules by which authority is exercised and decisions taken and implemented to manage all risk types and exposures.

DLT Providers need to deliver and maintain a corporate culture consistent with the secure and confident delivery of these principles. They need to have an open, cooperative and transparent relationship with the GFSC and other regulators and must disclose to them any matter of which the regulator would reasonably expect notice. Areas of focus will include:

- board structure, including composition to ensure that there is a good balance and mix of skills and experience to complement the business;
- adequate application of the four eyes principle; and
- application of mind and management from Gibraltar.

7. A DLT Provider must ensure that all systems and security access protocols are maintained to appropriate high standards.

All systems used should ensure the right level of access to authorised personnel with up to date monitoring systems. On-going and proactive security assessments should be conducted on DLT technologies to keep up to date with any new threats and potential vulnerabilities. These include:

- risk assessment of applications, underlying technology, and cybersecurity;
- policies, procedures and controls to ensure the delivery of this principle;
- skilled and experienced staffing;
- continuous vulnerability and threat analysis and assessment;
- continuous monitoring and response provisions; and
- independent compliance audit and reporting.

8. A DLT Provider must have systems in place to prevent, detect and disclose financial crime risks such as money laundering and terrorist financing.

DLT Providers must adequately apply anti-money laundering and counter terrorist financing preventive measures which are commensurate with their risks, and report suspicious transactions. DLT Providers need to be aware of the vulnerabilities of its products and services to financial crime risks and ensure that they implement measures to mitigate the risks. DLT Providers need to comply with the Proceeds of Crime Act and any guidance issued by the GFSC.

9. A DLT Provider must be resilient and must develop contingency plans for the orderly and solvent wind down of its business.

DLT Providers need to develop, test and maintain adequate business continuity, disaster recovery and crisis management plans. Preparedness for any potential threats or loss should form part of the disaster recovery plans as well as a well-managed and structured business continuity management process. Testing of the plans and its embedded processes should form part of the business model.

But all these actions could be considered only soft regulation approaches as it is very difficult to establish a harder regime as understood in traditional regulation of markets. Mainly because the concept of legal entities is nearly impossible to maintain with blockchain applications. All legal entities that can be defined as such are only gatekeepers of the underlying blockchain that exists virtually.

As mentioned before, the potential of blockchains can only be presumed today. As all stored data in distributed ledger cannot be corrupted, they are cryptographically validated data. To quote Leanne Kemp, CEO of Everledger, from the IBM Institute for Business Value report: «At its core, blockchain is a shared ledger that allows participants in a business network to transact assets where everyone has control but no one person is in control»⁶ Validated supply chains will be available to the consumers, healthcare data will be managed in blockchain consortia models, and financial trading platforms will be managed through blockchains. Smart contracts will facilitate, execute and enforce agreements through blockchain technology and will guarantee proper fulfilment of the agreement and secure storage of data. This technology will make the use of intermediaries and middlemen more and more neglectable. Government services will be offered digitally like Land-Registry, E-voting, Notary Public Services, Passports, ID's, and

⁶ IBM Institute for Business Value. Forward Together: Three ways blockchain Explorers chart a new direction. Global C-suite Study. 19th ed. // URL: <https://www-01.ibm.com/common/ssi/cgi-bin/ssialias?htmlfid=GBE03835USEN>.

Licenses which will be tamper-proofed and access to personal assets will be secure and readily available. The coming years will show an enormous development of blockchain technology impacting all aspects of life on a day to day basis. The main challenge for regulators and society is an increasing asymmetry between the blockchain industry, its stakeholders and the legal system and consumer. Today's approach by various governments to implement more and more legal restrictions on the internet will not prove sustainable⁷. All regulations and restrictions should consider the specific aspects of blockchains and cryptocurrencies and not diminish the potential positive effects of economic growth and innovation.

Conclusion

Blockchains and cybercurrencies are opening a challenging new development for legislative regulations and law enforcement in general but anti-trust and competition law in particular. The decentralized and autonomous technology and structure of blockchains and the complete independence of any state institutions and controls poses unseen challenges to both governments and international

institutions. Blockchains might prove to be agnostic to any jurisdictional rules based on traditional legislative understanding. Blockchain consortia using artificial intelligence will go beyond the market structure as we have it today. The blockchain software will trigger decisions and actions automatically and without interference of blockchain participants.

Such scenario will force authorities to become more pro-active in their planning and operational modus. Capacity building has to be emphasized to keep the asymmetry of information between regulators and industry as small as possible. Self-regulation by the market players will be necessary to support. Finally, any regulations and standards have to be internationally coordinated and have to stay flexible to react to any development of these technologies which asks for ongoing international analysis and monitoring of evolution and market changes.

Blockchain technology is definitely an unseen challenge to legislative and regulative authorities which is asking for massive capacity building and adjustments of existing legal frameworks to give an answer to the challenges of tomorrow.

REFERENCES

1. *Ajinkya M. Tulpule. Enforcement And Compliance In A Blockchain(ed) World // CPI (Competition Policy International). January 2017. URL: <https://www.competitionpolicyinternational.com/wp-content/uploads/2017/01/CPI-Tulpule.pdf>.*
2. *Boog Ch., Gottlieb B. Disputes in the context of blockchain applications // URL: <http://www.swlegal.ch/CMSPages/GetFile.aspx?disposition=attachment&nodeguid=9cbbaf0f-8781-431f-8702-6673a2b29ac5> (June 2017, Schellenberg Wittmer, Attorney at Law, Newsletter).*
3. *Brandman G., Thampapillai S. Blockchain — Considering the Regulatory Horizon // URL: <https://www.law.ox.ac.uk/business-law-blog/blog/2016/07/blockchain-considering-regulatory-horizon> (July 2016, University of Oxford, Faculty of Law, Business Law Blog).*
4. *Crypto Valley Association. Mission and Policy Framework/General Code of Conduct. 01.2018 // URL: <https://cryptovalley.swiss/codeofconduct/>.*
5. *Gibraltar Financial Services Commission. Distributed Ledger Technology Regulatory Framework. 01.2018 // URL: <http://www.gfsc.gi/dlt>.*
6. *Iansiti M., Lakhani K. R. The Truth About Blockchain // Harvard Business Abstract. 01/02 2017. URL: <https://hbr.org/2017/01/the-truth-about-blockchain>.*
7. *IBM Institute for Business Value. Forward Together: Three ways blockchain Explorers chart a new direction // Global C-suite Study. 19th ed. URL: <https://www-01.ibm.com/common/ssi/cgi-bin/ssialias?htmlfid=GBE03835USEN>.*
8. *Milnes M. Blockchain: Issue in Competition & Consumer Law. 26.05.2016 // URL: <https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/blockchain-issues-competition-consumer-law-michael-milnes>.*
9. *Nakamoto Satoshi. A Peer-to-Peer Electronic Cash System. 2000. // URL: <https://bitcoin.org/bitcoin.pdf> (November 2008).*

⁷ World Trends in Freedom of Expression and Media Development : UNESCO Global Report 2017/2018 // URL: http://www.unesco.de/fileadmin/medien/Dokumente/Kommunikation/EN_WTR_2017_Executive_Summary_web.pdf.

10. *Nixon M.* Bitcoin Foundation seeks legal protection from US currency regulation // Independent. 30.08.2017 URL: <http://www.independent.co.uk/news/business/news/bitcoin-foundation-legal-protection-us-currency-regulation-llew-claasen-cryptocurrency-bitlicence-a7919401.html>.
11. *Primavera de F.* We Must Regulate Bitcoin. Problem Is, We Don't Understand It. 03.01.2016 // URL: <https://www.wired.com/2016/03/must-understand-bitcoin-regulate/>.
12. *Shcherbak S.* How Should Bitcoin Be Regulated? // European Journal of Legal Studies. 2014. Vol. 7, Is. 1. URL: <http://www.ejls.eu/15/183UK.pdf>.
13. *Starodubcev D.* Bitcoin created a supranational economy // URL: <http://www.coinfox.info/news/persons/5109-dima-starodubcev-bitcoin-created-supranational-economy> (17 March 2016, CoinFox.info).
14. World Trends in Freedom of Expression and Media Development : UNESCO Global Report 2017/2018 // URL: http://www.unesco.de/fileadmin/medien/Dokumente/Kommunikation/EN_WTR_2017_Executive_Summary_web.pdf.